

Dry weight of striga plants uprooted from field plots planted to selected rice entries at 2 sites in South Nyanza District, western Kenya. ^a

Entry	Mbita Point, 1990 short rains		Ungoye, 1991 long rains	
	Dry wt (g/15m ² ± SD)	Rating ^b	Dry wt (g/15 m ² ± SD)	Rating ^b
IR38547-B-B-7-2-2	0.0 ± 0.0	HR	0.0 ± 0.0	HR
IR47255-B-B-5-4	0.0 ± 0.0	HR	6.0 ± 7.1	R
IR47697-4-3-1	0.0 ± 0.0	HR	0.0 ± 0.0	HR
IR49255-B-B-5-2	0.0 ± 0.0	HR	2.5 ± 3.8	R
B3913F-16-5-ST-42	4.5 ± 0.6	R		
Ble Chai	7.5 ± 0.6	R	6.5 ± 7.9	R
UPR103-80-1-2			6.0 ± 1.6	R
Nam Roo	1520.0 ± 45.8	HS	105.3 ± 156.8	S
ITA257	1251.0 ± 95.0	HS	73.0 ± 78.8	S
IR47686-B-B-2-2	1460.0 ± 90.0	HS	553.3 ± 811.4	HS
(susceptible check)				
IR47686-13-2-1	^c		489.0 ± 757.6	HS
CV	10.8		304.9	

^aData selected from 40 entries. ^bR = highly resistant, R = resistant, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible. ^cNot tested.

and rated as highly resistant (see table). Entries B3913F-16-5-ST-42 and Ble Chai had light infestation and were rated as resistant. The remaining striga-infested, stunted entries had drought-

like, leaf-wilting symptoms and were rated as susceptible to highly susceptible.

Ten entries were reevaluated during 1991 long-rains season (Mar-Jul) at

Ungoye (Eutric Cambisols, pH 6.1, CEC 48.2 meq/100 g soil, 0.2% N, 1.6% organic C, 98 meq P/100 g soil, 1,000 mm rainfall), about 40 km southwest of MPFS.

We planted entries in 3- x 5-m plots, replicated four times, in a randomized block design. Striga plants were removed 90 d after rice emergence from plots, dried, and weighed. Two of the four cultivars rated as highly resistant at Mbita Point were also highly resistant at Ungoye. Nam Roo and ITA257, rated as susceptible at Mbita Point, were moderately resistant to *S. hermonthica* at Ungoye, indicating a possible genetic variability of the populations. Check IR47686-B-B-2-2 was susceptible at both sites.

Our tests showed that some of these rice cultivars can possibly be used to breed for striga resistance in upland rice. □

Stress tolerance—drought

Performance of shallow water rice for drought tolerance

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We evaluated 22 shallow water rice entries for drought tolerance under field conditions. The experiment was laid out

Drought tolerance of best yielding entries, Tamil Nadu, India, 1990. ^a

Initial Evaluation Trial no.	Cross or variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	Plant height (cm)
11371	Pankaj/T141	2.3	101
10743	Orumundakam/CRR1	2.2	114
–	Pankaj	2.1	99
–	Salivahana	1.8	105
11522	Mahsuri/IR2071-176-1-1	1.2	90
9866	Pankai/Swarnadhan	1.2	105
	LSD (P = 0.05)	0.4	7

^aNo yield was measured for IET10658 (Phalguna/PTB21/PTB33), IET10717 (Phalguna/Andrewsali), IET10722 (Nagarjuna/ARC5984), IET10738 (IR36/OR127-1), IET10754 (Phalguna/Andrewsali), IET10761 (Nagarjuna/ARC5084), IET10785 (Phalguna/Andrewsali), IET10797 (CR149-288/T142), IET11524 (IR20/IR25), IET11525 (IR20/IR15), IET11537 (CR151/CR1014), IET11537 (Nagarjuna/Magila), IET311374 (CR130-36/Jaganath), IET11395 (IET6858/ARC6172), IET11396 (IET6858/ARC6172), and Nagarjuna.

in a randomized block design with three replications. Seeds were sown 25 Jun 1990 and transplanted on 19 Jul 1990 in the main field in 7- x 2-m plots and at spacing of 15 x 10 cm.

The crop was irrigated every 10 d until 55 days after sowing (DAS) after which irrigation was stopped. Rains occurred at 120-125 DAS (110 mm) and 150-165 DAS (200 mm). We scored drought tolerance and drought recovery at 105 DAS and 125 DAS using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. All rice entries were grown to maturity.

Drought during late vegetative phase (55-110 DAS) and milk stage (125-140 DAS) severely affected the entries. Only six of the 22 entries yielded grain (see table). All six had tip drying to 1/4 of the length of most leaves. The nonyielding entries were chaffy and had unfilled grains because of the drought at the milk stage.

IET11371, IET10743, and Pankaj recorded yields of ≥ 2.1 t grain/ha, and 70-89% of the plants recovered. In contrast, Salivahana, IET11522, and IET9866 yielded 1.2-1.8t grain/ha, apparently because only 40-60% of plants recovered. □

Stress tolerance—excess water

Screening of rice germplasm against natural flooding in Cambodia

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We collected 1,600 samples of traditional rice germplasm in 1990-91 from 13 of

Cambodia's 21 provinces with the help of officials in the Ministry of Agriculture's Agronomy Department. Most of the cultivars were from rainfed lowland fields. Apparent duplicates were removed, leaving 373 new cultivars. These were direct seeded on 13 Aug 1991 at Prey Phdau Research Station, Kampong Speu. Twenty-two of the 373 did not germinate. Floodwater inundated the field 8 d after sowing. Seedlings

remained submerged for 6 d in water up to a maximum depth of 150 cm.

We scored submergence tolerance on a 1-9 scale 5 d after the flood receded. Some degree of submergence tolerance (score 1-5) was recorded in 75% of the cultivars (Table 1). This percentage of submergence tolerance is more than 10 times more than the percentage of varieties showing submergence tolerance from 18,256 entries screened at IRRI. This greater submergence tolerance may be due to the greater frequency of flooding in Cambodia and the natural selection for submergence tolerance occurring in farmers' fields.

The severity of submergence used here was similar to that in tests of the International Rice Germplasm Center (IRGC) as scored in two common cultivars; Srau Timor (score 5 on both tests) and Srau Thougon (score 7 on our test and score 9 in IRGC tests). A submergence score of 1 was recorded for entries from 5 of 13 provinces (Table 2).

Submergence score of 3, however, was recorded for these entries from nine provinces: Bak Changkes, Damnoeub Krape, Khmao Kdet, Khnang Khmaing, Kho, Kmean Chmous, Kong Keo, Krachak Chhrouk, Krachak Ses, Neang

Table 1. Submergence tolerance score of 351 rice germplasm. Cambodia, 1991.

Submergence tolerance score	Entries (n = 351)		Entries (n = 18,256) scored at IRRI (%)
	no.	%	
1	8	2.3	2
3	34	9.7	1
5	220	62.7	2
7	67	19.0	5
9	22	6.3	91

Table 2. Outstanding submergence-tolerant rice germplasm (submergence score 1) from Cambodia, 1991.

Accession no.	Cultivar	Province from which collected
1364	Angkear	Kampong Thom
1441	Damnoeub Sabai Bat	Steung Treng
1442	Damnoeub Ses	Svay Rieng
1446	Damnoeub Tong Sanke	Pur Sat
1464	Khngeng	Kampong Chhnang
1467	Khmang Romeang	Kampong Chhnang
1488	Kong Sar	Kampong Thom
1489	Kong Say	Pur Sat

Noy, Damnoeub Thnot, Kantourt Sa, Khpor Daung, Neang Noury, Neang Noy, Neang Rose, Neang Rovis, Neang San Kok, Sneng, Bantey Meas, Kantuy Damrei, Khneng Chnot, Clay, Dang Dav, Kong Soy, Neang Yi, Kong Bak Roteh, Sevith, Ansar Chang Kom, Khpor Daung,

Ang Kourt, Kaun Chen, Khmao, and Kaun Trai.

Cultivars scoring 1 and 3 would be useful for areas where fields are flood-prone at the early vegetative stage. They can also be used as donors for breeding submergence-tolerant rices. □

Stress tolerance—adverse temperature

Evaluation of indica/japonica crosses during boro season in West Bengal

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Indica/japonica crosses have reportedly performed well in areas where low temperature inhibits rice crop growth and yield. Boro (dry season) rice grown after lowland or deepwater rice in West Bengal experiences low temperature (10-15 °C) during early growth stages. Low temperature lengthens the crop duration, putting the reproductive phase into summer (Apr-May). High air temperature (35-40 °C) and premonsoon rain during this period occasionally damage boro rice.

Farmers grow short- to medium-duration, semidwarf modern varieties (MV) that average 4-5 t grain/ha. The congenial climate, however, makes it feasible to increase yields above the present level.

Nineteen indica/japonica advanced lines were obtained from IRRI and evaluated for seedling vigor, earliness, and high grain yield. Traditional, tall, boro variety CB1 and the promising, short-duration MV UPR103-80 were also evaluated in on-farm trials at Sonarhati village, Chinsurah, during 1990-91 boro. Minimum temperature between sowing and 45 d after sowing (DAS) was 10.8-11.1 °C. Cold tolerance, based on the amount of leaf yellowing, was recorded at 15, 30, and 45 DAS in the seedbed. IR8866-30-3-1-4-2, IR39739-7-4-3-1, and IR52418-B-B-B-6-2-1 were promising for cold tolerance and increased grain yield. IR8866-30-3-1-4-2 had the best average cold tolerance score (see table).

CB1 was tallest at 45 DAS followed by IR8866-30-3-1-4-2, which had the highest leaf number at 45 DAS. Indica/japonica lines yielded 13-15% more grain than UPR103-80. Grain type of indica/japonica crosses was comparable with that of CB1 and UPR103-80. Indica/japonica derivatives can possibly be used for varietal development programs in boro rice. □

Cold tolerance and grain yield in promising indica/japonica crosses. Chinsurah, West Bengal, 1990-91 boro season.

Entry	Type	Av cold tolerance (0-9 scale)	Seedling ht (cm) at 45 DAS	Leaves (no.) at 45 DAS	Days to 50% flowering	Grain yield (t/ha)
IR8866-30-3-1-4-2	Indica/japonica	3.6	10.6	4.2	114	7.4
IR39739-7-4-3-1	Indica/japonica	4.0	9.0	3.2	116	8.0
IR52418-B-B-B-6-2-1	Indica/japonica	4.1	9.0	3.0	112	6.8
CB1	Tall indica	3.8	15.0	3.0	114	4.1
UPR103-80	Semidwarf indica	5.3	9.0	3.6	116	6.0
	Mean	4.2	10.5	3.4	114	6.6
	F value ^a	10.4**	41.3**	8.55**	10.5**	40.5**
	LSD (0.05)	0.6	0.5	1.4	0.6	0.6

^a*** = significant at the 1% level.